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MOTIVATION AND MONETARY INCENTIVES FOR SERVICEMEN OF THE ARMED FORCES OF THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION

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ABSTRACT

Main theoretical approaches to motivation definition were described in the article as well as results of secondary data analysis of representative sociological research, performed by Sociological Center of Russian Military Forces. Research was focused on financial incentive of military service in up-to-date conditions and allowed to determine main ways of system development.

The development of the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation is impossible without the introduction of social technologies. First of all, this concerns the management of the military-social sphere at all levels. Social management plays a key role in achieving the goals of social development, ensures the effectiveness of investments in the "human capital" of the army in conditions of not only limited resources, but also sufficient resources.

From the point of view of classical management, one of the elements of management is motivation, which operates at the individual level and is based on the use of various stimulating means and the creation of material and moral interest that encourages people to achieve high results in their work¹. The motivation mechanism is a serious tool for staff stabilization, improving the efficiency, effectiveness and quality of any organization's activities. The army is no exception.

Motivation occupies a leading place in the structure of personality. Motivation is a set of driving forces that motivate a person to an activity that has a certain target orientation.

The process of motivation (motivation) is built around the needs of a person, which are the main object of influence in order to motivations of a person to act. In the most general form, a need is a feeling of a lack of something that has an individualized character with all the generality of manifestation. Needs are the main source of human activity in both practical and cognitive activities.

There are quite a large number of motivational theories that try to give a scientific explanation of the phenomenon of motivation. For example, practical management is based on the so-called theories of motivation, among which there are substantive (or theories of needs) and procedural.

Meaningful theories are aimed at clarifying the causes of certain human behavior. At the heart of procedural theories is the question of the emergence of a certain behavior that directs this behavior, supports and stops. There are three main substantive theories of motivation: Maslow's hierarchy of needs, F. Herzberg's two-factor theory, and McClelland's theory of three needs.

Procedural theories of motivation seek to explain the emergence of purposeful behavior: how it is directed, maintained, and terminated. Their goal is not to study classification, but to understand how to manage the behavior of personnel.

There are four main procedural theories of motivation: the theory of expectation by V. Vroom, the extended model of expectation by L. Porter and E. Poehler, the theory of justice by J. Adams and the theory of amplification popularized by B. Skinner. These theories are based on I. Pavlov's concept that any human behavior is the result of the stimulus. Therefore, human behavior is influenced by rebuilding (changing) the environment or the process in which a person works. Human behavior is also determined by the result (consequences) of the type of behavior chosen in this situation.

Such a variety of approaches, the incessant growth of scientific publications on the topic of interest to the author and the ambiguity of interpretations of the basic concepts in this field of scientific knowledge indicate the imperfection of the theoretical understanding of this phenomenon.

The problems of motivation and stimulation in the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation were also considered by many representatives of science in various aspects. Among such works, one can note the research of N.V. Belousov, I.V. Grabovsky, O.S. Kovalenko, E.A. Morgulenko, A.S. Slivkov, A.I. Tyurin and many others.

It should be noted that the deterioration of the legal status of military personnel and their family members in the country during the years of market transformations, the low effectiveness of the transformations associated with the abolition of a number of benefits to military personnel and an insignificant increase in monetary allowances, have generally affected the prestige and attractiveness of military service. To remedy this situation, it is necessary first of all to ensure a decent standard of living for the officers of the Armed Forces.

Thus, motivation is a managerial function based on the priorities of business behavior and determines the conditions of interest in the result of activity and the desire to achieve a balance between the goals of the military organization and the goals of the officer.

For the successful work of the officers of the army and navy, it is necessary to recreate and develop a system of motivation and stimulation. The motivation system is a complex of material and non-material incentives designed to provide high-quality and productive work of military personnel, as well as to attract the most talented specialists to the military unit and retain them. The incentive system is a set of interrelated and complementary incentives, the impact of which activates human activity to achieve the set tasks¹.

Currently, the system of monetary incentives for military personnel has begun to work, the first funds have been received by the troops and now a certain part of the officers receives incomparably more monetary allowances than the bulk of the officers. According to the plan of the leaders of the Russian Ministry of Defense, this system should become an important element that stimulates a conscientious attitude to the performance of official duties.

In order to study the current state of motivation and incentive systems in the army and navy, as well as the results and effects of the system introduced by Order No. 400 of 2008 "On awarding money to officers of the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation", the author conducted a secondary analysis of representative sociological studies carried out by the Sociological Center of the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation.

The secondary data analysis is based on the results of a survey in which 73 officers participated as experts. Among the experts 11% are junior officers, 89% of experts are senior officers, of which 48% in the military rank of "colonel" or "captain of the 1st rank".

Experts were asked to evaluate the current system of moral and material incentives for military service.

According to experts, the existing system of moral and material incentives for military service does not ensure the maintenance of a proper level of competitiveness of military personnel for achieving high results in their official activities.

- In the literature there are practical recommendations for increasing the degree of satisfaction when exposed to material incentives, which can be formulated as follows:
- simplicity and clarity for each employee of the financial incentive system;
- flexibility of the financial incentive system, which allows you to immediately encourage every positive result of work;
- organization of incentives according to criteria that will be perceived by everyone as true;
- cost-effectiveness and psychological validity of the size of incentives (more and less, more often and less);
- formation of employees' sense of the fairness of material rewards with the help of the incentive system;
- contributing to the system of financial incentives to increase the interest of employees in improving their work;

There is a clear relationship between the results of everyone's work and the activities of the organization.

- In light of this, experts were asked to choose which indicators of military skill and professionalism of military personnel, in their opinion, should be financially stimulated. Among such indicators, experts noted the following:
- excellent ratings of the unit, military unit (ship) for the main types of combat training (88%);
- achieving high results in exercises (combat duty, long-distance hikes, combat patrols) (85%);
- mastery of one, two or more related specialties with confirmation of their high class qualifications (2-1 class or master of military affairs) (up to 80%); excellent marks of a serviceman in command training (78%), etc.

Material remuneration of military personnel, according to experts, should be commensurate with the level of their monetary allowance (40-50%) and be of a one-time nature, and decisions on their award should be made by the commander after collegial

discussion at meetings of officers (in public organizations of military personnel) and taking into account the public opinion of military personnel.

During the survey, experts proposed three main directions, which, in their opinion, should form the basis of a system of moral and material incentives for military personnel:

- stimulating professional growth and a positive attitude to the performance of their official duties of each serviceman within the units ("platoon-company");
- stimulation of units, military units (ships) by types of combat training and their functional purpose;
- stimulation of military personnel, units, military units (ships) based on the results of the training period, the school year, upon completion of exercises (combat duty, long-distance hikes, combat patrols, etc.).

It should be noted that the value of material incentives increases with a low level of provision for military personnel and, conversely, decreases with a significant increase in its average values.

Most often, material (monetary) incentives are used if it is possible to single out the result of an individual. Experts note that the current practice of material encouragement in the troops (forces) is not focused on supporting proactive, executive and disciplined military personnel, especially those of them who show a desire for professional mastery of military equipment and weapons. So, according to experts, their subordinates in 2007 were mainly encouraged: for success in combat training at the end of the year (40%); for diligence and distinction in the service (40%); on the occasion of the anniversary date (15%).

According to the author, monetary motivation alone is not enough. Thus, it is necessary to note the motivational value of the professional growth of military personnel, which actualizes the task of their professional training. Professional growth ensures satisfaction of the need for self-expression, contributes to obtaining a higher-paid position. Thus, an intangible incentive becomes an important factor in improving material well-being.

In the light of the study of intangible motivation, it is necessary to note the value component, which includes motivational formations that have value, significance for the individual and mainly affect the choice of ways, means and ways of implementing activities.

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